

"SHAJARAI TURK" AND ITS CONTENT

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Annotation : This article describes the work "Shajarayi Turk" by Abulgazi Bakhadir Khan.

Key words : Abulgazi Bakhadir Khan, "Shajarayi Turk", Khorezm.

"Shajarayi Turk" occupies an important place in the work of Abulgazi Bakhadir Khan both as a historical source and as an artistic-literary and political monument. "Shajarai Turk" contains historical events describing the history of Khorezm in the XVI-XVII centuries. In "Shajarayi Turk" prose fragments, narratives, and the author's own adventures and sufferings are so vividly reflected that it reads like a work of art. The information about the history of the Turkic peoples and the history of Khorezm in the works of Abulgazi Khan is of great importance. Also, Abulgazi, who is well acquainted with folklore, cites many myths and legends in these works.

Abulgazi's main goal in creating the work is not only to create the history of Genghis Khan's generation, but also to write down the history of the times of his ancestors who ruled Khorezm, that is, the history that was not written due to the neglect of his ancestors, and leave it to future generations. was: "But the carelessness of our ancestors and the stupidity of the people of Khorezm, these two reasons caused the death of the fathers of Abdullahan (Shaybani Abdullahan II (1583-1598)) and our

fathers (Shaybani Yadgorkhan (15th century)) continued their history from the place where they left until they came to us.

We thought that we should offer this history to someone, but we did not find a suitable person, it was necessary (and) we told it ourselves. There is a Turkish proverb: " O' ksuz uz kindigin o' zi kesar" tegan"¹.

The criterion that determines the uniqueness of each writer is his style. The variety of styles in it means that the writer has many different sides. From this point of view, the work "Shajarayi Turk" is considered one of the rare masterpieces of the 17th century. This work is a treasure trove of important information like Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's "Baburnoma". Just like "Boburnoma", in this work, the author's memories of the past and the times he lived in, what he saw and heard, what he read and what he knew are described in a strict form, systematically and consistently.

There is one central idea that stands out in the ideological tools of Abulgazi Bakhadir Khan's work "Shajarayi Turk", which is to glorify the idea of creating a large centralized feudal state and condemn the chaos-leadership. This ideological orientation defines the writer's unique style, unique and unique image methods of the work ². There is chronological consistency in the description of historical events in "Shajarayi Turk". It describes the origin of man from religious legends to the events of the 17th century.

The work consists of 9 chapters, each of which consists of separate short stories.

Chapter 1 is called " **Remembrance of God's creation of man, peace be upon him.**" It contains information about the creation of man and similar information as found in other historical works.

¹ Abug' oziy. Shajarayi turk. - T.: Cho' lpon, 1992. - B.5

² Xudoy nazarov H. "Shajarayi turk" va uning o'rganilishi. T.: 1993.

Chapter 2 is called "**The mention of Mongol Khan until the birth of Genghis Khan**" and it contains important information about the history of the formation of the Mongol tribes and their military campaigns.

Chapter 3 is called "**Remembrance of the Birth of Genghis Khan**" , and this chapter contains the legend of his birth and the information that he became a Khan and led many wars and great military campaigns.

Chapter 4 is called "**Mention of Genghis Khan's third son, Ogaday Qon, and everyone from Genghis Khan's descendants who reigned in Mongolia.**"

Chapter 5 is called "**Mention of Chingiz Khan's second son Chigatai Khan and his descendants who reigned in Movarunnahr and Kashgar**" .

Chapter 6 is called "**Remembrance of the reign of Genghis Khan's younger son Toli Khan in the land of Iran**"

Chapter 7 is called "**The mention of Jochikhan's descendants ruling in Dashti Kipchak**" .

Chapter 8 is called "**The mention of the reign of Shayban Khan, the fifth son of Jochi Khan bin Genghis Khan, who reigned in Turan and Kazak and Crimea and Movarunnahr.**"

The 9th chapter is called "**Remembrance of the reign of Khorezm from the descendants of Shayban Khan, the fifth son of Jochi Khan bin Genghis Khan.**" This chapter, which occupies the main part of the work, contains very valuable information about the history of Khorezm.

In general Abulgazi history to know in the field himself lived period equal no one person the fact that to everyone known. He is Turkish nations to history about legend and the narrations are also popular of historians many books too perfect learned and traditions continue own of the dynasty write the rest history write, own to his descendants gift did is a historian.

Abulgazi Bakhadir Khan " own of his work wide spread provide wide spreading provide and effect strength increase in order to proverb and from fairy

tales creative uses , art image tools uses Of these all " Family tree of the Turk educational importance increases , simple in sentences temperature with described event and memories person to himself fascination will ... Nature scenery , battle plates , swords sound and of people his cry when describing the words used are also artistic expression the style of the reader it's fun .³

"Turkish family tree" own mother that's it aspects with another history from his books difference does Abulgazin historical from sources the most reliable ones choose to know, har how to fabrications given not going , often unbiased road catch to him fame brought Of these that's all joined " Shajarayi Turkish " pure historical work being without staying , maybe historical and artistic work shape from receiving proof will give .

References

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- 2 Abulg‘ozi Bahodirxon. Shajarayi turk. Toshkent: Cho‘lpon, 1992.
- 3 Дженкинсон А. Путешествие в Среднюю Азию 1558-1560гг. Английские путешествие в Московском государстве в XVI веке. Перевод с английского Л.Готье. Л.:1932.

³ Abdullayev V.A. O`zbek adabiyoti tarixi. T., 1964, 16-bet.